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**TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF POSTNATAL ENDOMETRITIS
IN PRODUCTIVE COWS.**

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Summary: The article studied the effectiveness of the drug Ixglucovite-vet in the treatment of acute and purulent-catarrhal endometritis in cows after a birth.

Key words: UTT apparatus, Ixglucovit-vet, rectal, clamping, TB oxytocin, acute endometritis, uterine involution.

Relevance of the topic. Animal husbandry is an important branch of Agriculture of our country, it is important to ensure employment and income of the rural population, to satisfy the demand of the domestic consumer market for environmentally friendly, high-quality livestock products. In our country, a great emphasis is placed on establishing the livestock sector on a scientific basis, increasing their productivity by applying advanced technologies to production, modern scientific achievements. From research, I found out that in livestock farms, up to 12-25% of cows remain infertile throughout the year, in some farms this indicator is up to 30-35%. The main reasons why cows become infertile are postnatal placenta retention, different types of endometritis, as well as embryo death.

The purpose of the study. Determination, treatment and Prevention of the degree of incidence of obstetric-gynecological diseases among dairy cows on livestock farms and which gynecological disease occurs most often. On farms, it was found that the

post-birth placenta was caught among cows and endometritis were abundant, and testing the drug Ixglucovit-vet in the treatment and Prevention of endometritis.

Object and styles of research. Studies were carried out on cows on livestock farms specialized in the cultivation of dairy products of the Kashkadarya and Samarkand regions. The studies were carried out by clinical and rectal examination of the causes of barren cows being separated from the herd and Barking in the rectal and UTT apparatus of cows on the farm. In the tests, treatment was carried out with separation in the alox of cows, whose companion was caught and infected with endometritis.

Results and their analysis. The work to determine the healing effect of the drug Ixglyukovit-vet was carried out in 3 groups of cows infected with endometritis. 8 head of cows in the control group after the uterus is lightly massaged and washed for 2-3 minutes (with 1-5000 fluids of rivanol). In addition, on the 1st day of treatment, a 2% fat solution of sinestrol was administered from 2 ml to the muscle and on the 2nd, 5th under the skin in the amount of 40 TB oxytocin and penstrep antibiotic 20 kg/TV 1 ml to the muscle.

Cows with 13 head of purulent-catarrhal endometritis in the 1 group in the experiment were treated by lightly massaging the uterus for 2-3 minutes and injecting (rivanol 1-5000) with its liquid, injecting into the uterus 20-25 ml of the drug Ixglyukovit-vet every 3 days through a syringe catheter.

Table 1.

In the treatment of purulent-catarrhal endometritis after the birth of cows, the effect of the drug xglucovit-vet

Groups	Used preparations quantity	Cows number	From this recovered		Walking barren days	Became infertile	Fatherland
			Prime	Percentage			
Experiment group 1	The drug ixglucovit-vet was administered	13	13	100	55,8	0	13 100%

	into the uterus from 20-25 ml and treated						
Experiment group 2	The drug Ixglyukovit-vet was treated by subcutaneous administration every 100 kg of t/v 5 ml	10	9	90,0	66,5	1	9 90,0%
Control group	General treatment method applied	8	6	75,0	77,4	2	6 75,0%

The 10 head cows in the 2nd group in the experiment were treated by massaging the uterus and sending 2 ml of surfagon drug between the muscles after washing, and 5 ml to 5000) of liquid per 100 kg of live weight into the uterus every 3 days from 20 to 25 ml of the drug Ixglyukovit-vet under the skin on the 1st and 7th.

After dilution with 5000) in the first treatment of 13 head cows in the 1st experimental group, 20-25 ml of Ixglucovit-vetpreparate every 3 days into the uterus can also heal 10 heads of 76.9% from cows in the group applied into the uterus, and the remaining 3 heads (100%) in the second treatment. They were found to have been infertile for 58 days and were fattened upon examination through the rectum 2 months after fertilization by a complete anthrax.

In the second Experimental Group, 10 head cows are treated with 5000) fluid in the first treatment, after 20-25 ml of Ixglucovit-vetpreparate every 3 days into the uterus with 5 ml per 100 kg of live weight when treated using subcutaneous 8 head (80.0%) cows and in the second treatment 9 head (90.0%) recovers. they were braked 1 Head of cattle if they had been infertile for 65 days, 9 Head of cattle were found to have been fattened when examined through the rectum after 2 months.

Of the 8 head cows in control, 4 heads (50.0%) recovered in the first treatment, while 2 heads recovered in the 2nd treatment, for a total of 6 heads (75.0%). It was

found that their barking days were 74 days, with 2 heads of treated cows being infertile and 6 heads being fattened when examined through the rectum after 2 months.

In the treatment of postnatal purulent-catarrhal endometritis in cows (rivanol 1-5000), after dilution, it was found that the treatment method of injecting 20-25 ml into the uterus every 3 days Ixglucovit-vet into the uterus is more effective than subcutaneous administration and has a higher effect of injecting cows by ingestion. We recommend this method of treatment to practice.

The work to determine the healing effect of ixglukovit-vet was carried out in 3 groups of cows with acute endometritis. After the uterus of 10 head cows in the control group was lightly massaged for 2-3 minutes and washed (rivanol 1-5000), the drug yodapen was administered into the uterus against microorganisms. In addition, on the 1st day of treatment, a 2% fat solution of sinestrol was administered from 2 ml to between the muscles and on the 2, 5th days, 40 TB of oxytocin under the skin and 20 kg/TV 1 ml of the penstrep antibiotic between the muscles.

In cows with 15 head of acute endometritis of the 1st group in the experiment, 2 ml of the drug Cloprostin was administered between the muscles, the uterus was lightly massaged for 2-3 minutes and after washing (1-5000 rivanol) was treated with a liquid, into which 20-25 ml of danixglucovite-vet syringe was administered through a catheter every 3 days. The 13 head cows in the experimental group 2 were treated after the uterus was massaged and washed, with 2 ml of the drug Cloprostin between the muscles, and 5 ml for every 100 kg of live weight, sent under Ixglyukovit-vetteri on the 1st and 7th.

Table 2

The effect of Ixglucovite-vetpreparate in the treatment of acute endometritis after the birth of cows

Groups	Used preparations quantity	Cows number	From this recovered		Walking barren days	Became infertile	Fatherland
			Prime	Percentage			
Experiment group 1	The drug ixglucovit-vet	15	15	100	61	1	14 93,3%

	was administered into the uterus from 20-25 ml and treated						
Experiment group 2	The drug Ixglyukovit-vet was treated by subcutaneous administration every 100 kg of t/v 5 ml	13	12	92,3	65	2	11 84,6%
Control group	General treatment method applied	10	8	80,0	76	3	7 70,0%

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It was found that in the first treatment of 15 head cows in the 1st experimental group, the drug Ixglucovit-vet also recovers 13 heads 86.6% from cows in the group applied into the uterus, and the remaining 3 heads (100%) in the second treatment. Their barren days were 61 days, and it was found that 1 Head of cattle was not fattened when the cured cows were fertilised and the remaining 14 heads were fattened. The rate of firing was 93.3%.

In the first treatment of 13 head cows in the second Experimental Group, 10 head (76.9%) cows were cured when treated using subcutaneous support from 5 ml per 100 kg of live weight, and 12 head (92.3%) cows in the second treatment, and 2 head cows turned out to be infertile if their days were 65 daysThe paternity rate was 84.6%.

The 10 head cows that were under control had 6 heads (60.0%) in the first treatment, and 8 heads (80.0%) in the 2nd treatment had 76 days of their infertility, while 3 heads of treated cows were found to be infertile and 7 heads were found to be straitened when rectal tested 2 months later.The rate of paternity was 70.0%.

In the treatment of acute postnatal endometritis in cows, ixglucovit-vet intrauterine administration is more effective than subcutaneous administration, and shows a higher result in cows being shot by ingestion.

In the treatment of acute postnatal endometritis in cows, Ixglucovite-vettpreparate injection into the uterus and subcutaneous injection methods have shown higher efficacy than the method of treatment of controlled animals. In addition, the drug has a good effect in reducing the period of barren Walking of cows. We recommend this method of treatment to practice.

The drug Ixglukovit-vet, which has a good effect in the treatment of postnatal venereal diseases in cows, was tested in order to study its effectiveness in preventing postnatal diseases in cows, to improve the course of uterine involution in bovine and euthanized cows.

In order to study the effect of prophylaxis of the drug Ixglyukovit-vet from diseases after the birth of cows, research was carried out on 15 head of bull cows. In the experimental cows, the amount of use of the drug xglyukovit-vet was also studied.

Table 3

Ixglyukovit-vetpreparatini effect in preventing post-natal disease of cows

№	Group s	The procedure for using rugs(between the muscles)	Head umber	From this birth next infected	
				Head umber	%
1	I group	Ixglyukovit-vet preparation when 2 times	8	2	25,0
2	II control s	When Trivit is applied 2	7	4	57,1

The 15 head bull cows allocated for the experiment were divided into 2 groups. The 8 head cows in the first group were sent 10-15 days before giving birth 2 times, and on the day of the birth, the fourth group (control) trivit was sent 10-15kun to give birth 2 times in the amount of 10 ml and on the day of the birth.

Clinical trials revealed a 50% decrease in fertility in cows after administration of the drug Ixglyukovit-vet, postpartum placenta retention, and endometritis. It was found in the experiment that the drug Ixglyukovit-vet has a high effect in preventing the incidence of postnatal diseases with a mild course of labor in cows sent 2 times.

CONCLUSION: In the treatment of acute and purulent-catarrhal endometritis after giving birth in cows, it was found that the method of treatment by injecting Ixglucovit-vetbachadone into it is more effective than subcutaneous administration and has a higher effect on the excretion of cows by ingestion. The high efficiency and low cost of the drug in the Prevention of post-birth diseases of cows decreased by 25.0% in 2 applications, that is, 2 weeks before the birth of cows and 25.0% after the birth of cows when applied on the day of birth.

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